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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

side, suggesting significant retention in tissue. MNP transport between maternal and fetal side and MNP uptake by placental tissue were studied. All three particle sizes used were found back in the perfused tissue. Smaller particles exhibited a greater tendency to agglomerate around villi compared to larger particles. The perfusion solution on the fetal side showed increased fluorescence after perfusion with 1 μ m particles, indicating that a part had crossed to the fetal side, as is also observed with CFM. Smaller particles were retained in the tissue to a greater extent, i.e., 92% and 63% were retained for 50 nm and 200 nm, while only 26% of the 1 μ m particles were retained. Next steps include the prevention of clustering of smaller particles during perfusion, as well as perfusions with other MNP polymer types synthesized by our research group. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under AURORA grant agreement No 964827.

1.09.C.T-04 Probabilistic Human Risk Assessment of Micro/Nanoplastics: Integrating the Aggregate Exposure Pathway and Adverse Outcome Pathway (AEP-AOP)

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Microplastic particles are ubiquitous in the environment, found in everything from the air we breathe to the food we eat. Despite progress in microplastic research, evaluating the human health risks of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) remains challenging due to their varied characteristics and multiple pathways. This study aims to assess the human health risks of MNPs by applying an Aggregate Exposure Pathway and Adverse Outcome Pathway (AEP-AOP) framework integrated with a Bayesian network, taking into account the material properties and multi-media characteristics of MNPs. To enhance the risk assessment of MNPs on human health, several key methodologies were adopted. First, a quality assurance and control (QA/QC) screening process was implemented to ensure data reliability. QA/QC criteria filtered non-standard exposure and toxicity data from the literature, and only datasets meeting these standards were included in the analysis. Next, data alignment methods using parameterized probability density functions (PDFs) were applied to better reflect real-world conditions. Exposure data were standardized by size range, while toxicity data were adjusted to reflect the polydispersity of environmental MNPs and biologically relevant size fractions. Following data alignment, a Cumulative Risk Assessment (CRA) was conducted. An AEP-AOP network was constructed from a comprehensive literature review and the AOP wiki database to integrate the diverse exposure pathways of microplastics. Key event relationships were further assessed using a Bayesian network modeling approach, which improved the network's reliability by analyzing probabilistic relationships. Based on the AEP, total daily exposure to MNPs was calculated, and Margin of Exposure (MoE) values were derived for each key event within the AOP to assess potential risks. This study provides a robust framework for next-generation human risk assessments of MNPs, utilizing an AEP-AOP approach integrated with Bayesian networks to address the complex properties of MNPs through various advanced methodologies. Additionally, the NGRA results identified oral ingestion as the primary human exposure route, underscoring potential developmental risks associated with MNP exposure. These findings emphasize the need for further in-depth research to examine the multi-media exposure pathways and developmental toxicity of MNPs. This work was supported by Korea Environment Industry & Technology Institute (KEITI) through Technology Development Project for Safety Management of Household Chemical Products, funded by Korea Ministry of Environment (MOE)(RS-2023-00215309)

1.09.C.T-05 Biological Evaluation of Binding of Toxins to Microplastics

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Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) contaminate ecosystems worldwide and enter our food and water via the aquatic environment or plastic food containers. MNPs could serve as carriers of aquatic or food pathogens and/or their toxins, facilitated by their large surface area and hydrophobic nature. However, there is currently no method for qualitative or quantitative evaluation of toxin binding to MPs. This study focuses on cereulide (CER) and fumonisin B1 (FB1) as model toxins, examining their binding to microplastics (MPs) composed of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polypropylene (PP) under simulated environmental and biological conditions. It aims to evaluate the binding of toxins to MPs by assessing the subsequent biological effects using advanced cell-based models and analysis techniques. The work is part of the EU-funded IMPTOX project, aiming to unravel the mechanisms of MP-toxin interactions and their implications for human exposure and toxicity. An optimized 3D in vitro cell model assisted in exposing hepatic HepG2 spheroids to the different conditions. The spheroids were chronically exposed to MPs that

were pre-incubated for 2 hours with the toxins. Using IncuCyte Sx5 Live Cell Analysis and Agilent Seahorse extracellular flux analysis, the cells' bioenergetic responses were monitored. Shifts in metabolic parameters for bound toxin-MPs versus the MPs or toxins alone indicate that this biological approach could serve as an effective proxy to investigate toxin-MP binding. This research has been funded by IMPTOX European Union s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant number 965173), Research Foundation Flanders research grant 1506419N, Ghent University Special Research Fund grant BOF20/BAS/120, The Federal Public Service (FPS) Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment project RT 21/5 CYANTIR and Research Foundation Flanders/ Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency Weave project with grant number G000123N. M.F.A. received a postdoctoral mandate funded by Ghent University Special Research Fund (BOF) grant number BOF01P03220.

1.09.P Impact of Micro- and Nanoplastics on Environmental and Human Health: Monitoring, Fate, Exposure, Toxicity and Mechanisms of Toxic Action

1.09.P-Mo058 Micro- and Nanoplastics Libraries Reflecting Environmental Physicochemical Properties

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Microplastics (MPs), defined as plastic particles smaller than 5 mm, are found widely across the environment, while nanoplastics (NPs) are classified as particles under 1 μm in size. The recent discovery of MPs in human tissues such as the lung, placenta, and blood underscores their human exposure through inhalation or ingestion. MPs and NPs (MNPs) are also prevalent in diverse environments, including air, rivers, and even drinking water. However, their full impact on human health remains largely uncertain. Although MNPs exhibit varied physicochemical properties (e.g., size, shape, and surface oxidation induced by environmental factors like UV radiation), research often overlooks these complexities when evaluating their biological effects. Consequently, particles representing environmentally relevant MPs and NPs are scarce, with most studies relying on plastic particles with limited physicochemical diversity due to availability. To address this gap, we are working on development of MNPs libraries that consider size, shape, surface oxidation of environmental MNPs. We selected polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as target polymers based on their high global production. Fragmented particles for each polymer, ranging from NPs to MPs in size, were prepared. In addition, surface-oxidized MPs (oxiMPs) were produced by irradiating them with 172 nm vacuum UV light in air, simulating environmental conditions. For comparison, environmental MPs were collected from a sandy beach along Osaka Bay. Analytical techniques such as ATR-IR revealed hydroxy and carbonyl groups on both the environmental MPs and oxiMPs. To create smaller particles (NPs, under 1 μm in diameter), we employed a previously reported precipitation-based method. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed the successful production of NPs particles. In order to kinetics analysis, we used Nile Red to tag each MNPs, achieving successful labelling, and further adapted the protocol to incorporate Qdot, a bright and photostable fluorescent label, for NP labelling, validated via microscopy. These MNPs libraries, which reflect complex physicochemical properties, enhance the applicability of MNPs research to real-world environmental contexts. They are available for collaborative distribution upon request. This research was performed by the Environment Research and Technology Development Fund (JPMEERF20241003) of the Environmental Restoration and Conservation Agency provided by Ministry of the Environment of Japan and the Sumitomo Foundation for Environmental Research Projects.

1.09.P-Mo059 Detection of Internalized Nanoplastics in Human Cells Using Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS)

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Nanoplastics (< 100 nm) represent one of today's most pressing environmental and health challenges. Compared to larger plastic particles, nanoplastics exhibit increased bioavailability, which can significantly elevate ecological and human health risks. Despite their widespread occurrence, the understanding of how